

SUNRISE

Sustainable Urban Neighbourhoods
Research and Implementation
Support in Europe

D3.1

Co-Implementation Guidelines

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Certain co-words belong to specific phases along the entire innovation chain. This is depicted in the workflow diagram of the SUNRISE project (see figure 2).

Figure 2: Pert Chart of the SUNRISE project

The following table maps various words that can be found in the literature to their corresponding counterpart in the SUNRISE terminology:

	→ Sequential phases along the entire innovation chain →			
Literature ¹	Co-production			
	Co-creation			
	Co-commission	Co-design	Co-deliver	Co-assess
SUNRISE	Co-identify & co-validate	Co-develop & Co-select	Co-implement & co-create	Co-evaluate & co-assess
	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4

¹ For example: Governance International, 2006. See <http://www.govint.org/our-services/co-production/>

4. Why do it?

It is entirely legitimate to ask about the added value of an approach that implies a deviation from established ways of doing things. In fact, co-creation in general and co-implementation in particular should be pursued only if everyone involved is convinced of its advantages and not because it is fashionable. The following overview articulates some of the more important potential benefits of co-implementation, without any claim of comprehensiveness and without any assurance that all of them will materialise to the same degree.

Potential cost savings are very likely benefits of co-implementation activities because certain types of resources, be they time, skills, money etc. are being contributed that would not be mobilised in a traditional service delivery model. For example, the municipality of Uplengen (see below) saved about €500,000 in the seven years during which it cooperated with citizens in the construction of so called “citizen cycling lanes” (Bürgerradwege). Cost savings should not, however, be the only motivation of co-implementation approaches because of a very real risk of civic contributors being exploited (see above).

Mobilisation of local know-how:

The involvement of local citizens always also entails the mobilisation of these citizens’ local know-how. This can be knowledge about locally specific cultures, communication channels, rat run paths, historical references, collective memories, dialects, micro-infrastructures, everyday routines etc. A lot of this knowledge would be inaccessible to and remains dormant under conventional implementation activities.

Exposure to reality: Initiatives of the city administrations do not typically need to prove their financial survivability in the competitive climate of the market economy. This can amount to “too much shelter” from selection pressures and even to the protection of concepts which are actually not viable in the long term. The systematic involvement of local stakeholders or businesses in the implementation effort can expose an idea early on to a limited degree of this harsh reality and thus facilitate its fine-tuning to enable its long-term survival even after the initial public kick-start funding has ended (see Hoogma et al. 2002).

Residents: People living in proximity of a particular measure are, by definition, affected by it. It can therefore be assumed that they care about what happens and it happens; they also tend to possess particular local knowledge and contacts. In many areas, existing neighbour associations are a good entry point into this community. They are sometimes organised as official associations and sometimes convene virtually through neighbourhood portals or social media groups.

Businesses, especially those that are located within or near the intervention area, should be considered as potential co-implementation allies because they can benefit greatly from a range of improvements; be it safer and more pleasant streets, more seating opportunities, noise reductions, clearer and more reliable transport information etc. They also tend to respond positively to opportunities to boost their reputation. Business owners can be approached individually and directly or via their associations like Chamber of Commerce.

Transport service providers like bus operators, taxi companies, car and bike rental companies etc. can be natural allies in co-implementation efforts if the planned measures are likely to increase or stabilise their customer base. They are also typically interested to get involved if they can get associated with an initiative that is widely perceived as positive, especially in the area of transport and mobility.

Local artists, including painters, sculptors, galleries, musicians from Baroque singers to local punk-rock bands can play a valuable role in co-implementation efforts. They might have refreshingly unconventional ideas, draw the attention of the general public as well as the media or even produce some artefacts such as murals, sculptures etc. Artists often appreciate opportunities to show their talent and - depending on their level of professionalism - might even become active just for fun (e.g. school bands).

Emergency services such as the police or fire brigades sometimes have a public mandate for active involvement in improvements to the local community and sometimes they can have a genuine interest in the effects of certain measures because if can make their work easier. An example is the active participation of the fire brigades in Bremen, who demonstrated tangibly the importance of clamping down on illegal parking - simply because their fire truck could not access certain streets.

Clubs and special interest groups without a particular normative agenda can also play an important role. After all, members of a chess club, rabbit breeders and sports enthusiasts are residents, commuters, they have children etc. which typically represents a connection point to topics around sustainable mobility. Such groups might not get engaged because of a general underlying mission but they nevertheless can be very important communicators and amplifiers.

- Certain professional groups like lawyers, journalists, planners, architects etc.;
- Students;
- Disability groups;
- Visitors, providing a fresh outsider view.

The above list is of course far from exhaustive. Every situation is different and therefore the range of individuals and organisations with a motivation to actively engage in co-implementation activities is different.

6. Possible contributions

As with the above list of potential contributors, the following list of potential types of contributions must not be considered comprehensive. But it is at least intended as source of inspiration to trigger ideas about what kind of activities certain civic actors might be able and willing to engage in.

Maintenance: Tree-adoption programmes are almost like the poster children of co-implementation activities. Typically, the city provides training, sometimes tools and insurance for citizens who volunteer to look after trees and/or the flowerbeds around city-owned trees. Understood more broadly, the co-maintenance principle can also apply more widely to a “clean up your street”, re-freshing the paint on a bench etc.

Figure 5: A flower-bed with adoption sign © R. Brand

Light labour can encompass maintenance activities (see above) but also the creation of certain measures in the first place like the painting of a mural. In both cases, care needs to be taken not to run into liability issues resulting from health and safety regulations - see below in the section on Risks. This kind of contribution can also include the production of certain prototypes; good organisations to approach in this context are DIY organisations under names such as fab-labs, maker spaces etc.

Access to communication channels might not be the first thought when talking about co-implementation but it might well be one of the most important types of contributions. Many civic groups have very large and effective communication vehicles such as newsletters, magazines, mailing lists etc. The permission to feed messages into these channels can be particularly important to mobilise understanding, appropriate usage of and care for the actual core measure.

Endorsement is closely related to the above point. The specific aspect here is not only the quantitative reach of certain communication channels but their trustworthiness and credibility. For example, if the priest explains and endorses a certain measure during the Sunday mass, this can carry invaluable weight among the audience. Statements from local celebrities, radio hosts, football stars, musicians, aldermen and -women etc. can have similar effects.

Acting as public champion is closely related to the above point of “endorsement”. However it is one thing to publicly praise a measure, for example, the opening of a new CarSharing station; it carries much more meaning, of course, if a well-known and well-respected person actually uses it ... and ideally posts about on its social media channel.

The **provision of training and mentoring** can be extremely valuable to ensure the safe and appropriate use of certain infrastructures and devices. This can be as basic as “travel buddies” who demonstrate the use of public transport ticket machines to older people or volunteers who teach others how to ride a bicycle. An important aspect in this context is trust and, correspondingly, a low risk of embarrassment for the learners.

Problem reporting can be a very basic form of contributions to co-implementation activities. A relatively widespread application of this principle is the reporting of potholes through attentive citizens. This can be facilitated through convenient reporting mechanisms such as a smartphone app (see www.jarokelo.hu as a particularly impressive example). Similar examples include the reporting of broken light bulbs, graffiti, illegal rubbish heaps, broken elevators, etc.

Hosting role: Certain initiatives exist where citizens or businesses agree to act as “host” of some kind of publicly accessible asset. An example is the eCargo-Bike sharing scheme www.donk-ee.de in Germany. The bikes are provided by a company, but their batteries are regularly charged by a voluntary host who also checks the air pressure in the tyres and removes any waste from the cargo box. In return, the host gets a certain number of free usage hours per month.

Providing existing data: Some organisations, for example businesses, possess valuable data, e.g. postcodes or trip modes of their customers. In anonymised and aggregated formats such data can be shared with municipal partners for implementation related purposes.

Crowdsourced data, especially geo-referenced data is an area of ICT applications with enormous growth potential and with a necessary role of citizens as contributors. Examples include apps which allow users to rate their subjective experience while cycling or walking along a certain route in terms of safety, noise, beauty etc. This makes it possible to calculate navigation recommendations to suit specific preferences (e.g. www.safeandthecity.com)

Organising / hosting of events: Such a contribution can take the shape of someone providing their parking lot for an event at no costs while the city covers related expenses for technical equipment, catering etc. Or someone organises and pays for an event to promote sustainable mobility in some sense and the city endorses it publicly and arranges the required permissions.

The Leefstraat concept², popular in Belgium, would be an example of such a collaborative effort.

Financial contributions: This category of contributions comes in a number of different shapes. It includes straightforward donations, although this might be relatively rare. It also includes sponsorships, typically by private companies, in exchange of some favourable mention (e.g. in press releases), the display of logos on flyers and posters etc. Also fundraising falls into this category and so does crowd-funding

Crowd-investment can be considered a specific form of financial contributions from civic actors. A typical case would be if citizens contribute to a public investment, public infrastructure or public service (e.g. the purchase of an electric bus to replace an old diesel bus) and expect some kind of legitimate return, be it monetary or in the form of rebates like free bus rides for a certain period. This option can be particularly interesting if banks refuse to invest or if they request unreasonably high interest rates.

Commitment to upgrade own infrastructure, hardware: An example of this type of contribution was mentioned in the above hypothetical case study: “Employers agreed on a five-year programme to install showers for their employees.” Similar examples would be the commitment to install bike racks on private properties, to improve lighting on private streets, to cut back shrubs reaching from a private garden into the sidewalk etc.

Skills, know-how and ideas can be extremely valuable contributions, which some citizens will contribute. This can be formal knowledge such as professional judgements on the technical feasibility of a certain measure (e.g. from a retired engineer) or the translation of a flyer into a different language. It can also be tacit knowledge such as the local knowledge about spots which are perceived as unsafe or something as basic as a creative idea about the shape of a bench..

Providing positive feedback. It seems very common among many people to complain about problems - and rightly so. What sometimes tends to be forgotten is the public expression of praise for something well done. It can therefore be of value to encourage people to write positive letters to the newspaper, to speak up in public hearings etc. This is not bribery or collusion if it is genuine and simply gives voice to a silent majority.

7. Risks and challenges

Co-implementation is not a routine approach, it is not suitable for every situation, it requires the courage to try out something new, it requires the acceptance of certain risks - and it can go wrong. It is therefore important to realistically assess various risks and challenges, to avoid

² <https://www.leefstraat.be/the-ghent-pioneering/>

overly optimistic expectations and to prevent foreseeable problems. If done well, the benefits of co-implementation can outweigh the risks by far!

Liability: If something goes wrong that was implemented in a conventional way, it is at least clear who is liable, whose insurance pays, who remedies the problem. If citizens or other stakeholders are part of the implementation team, however, mistakes or accidents can have particularly tricky implications. It is therefore very important to be very clear about responsibilities, to explicitly unburden civic contributors - especially volunteers - from any liability and/or to organise sufficient insurance cover for them. This is the duty of the municipality.

Reliability: If civic co-implementers assume their role on a voluntary basis, they are exempt, by definition, of any contractual obligation to execute anything in any particular way within any particular timeframe. If they decide or have to withdraw their commitment for any reason this can sometimes jeopardise a larger project. Care should therefore be taken to only allocate core elements of an initiative to civic actors with a proven track record or at least with a firm and realistic commitment and with robust organisational structures. It is also advisable to establish early warning procedures.

Lack of coordination: The non-contractual nature of many civic actors' contributions can make it difficult if not impossible to demand their presence at meetings or their adherence to specific standards, timings etc. This can result in rather uncoordinated activities to a waste of time and many and, in the worst case, to mistakes and counterproductive results. To prevent this from happening, a culture of clear, frank and proactive communication should be established with suitable communication channels.

Lack of contributors: By its very nature, co-implementation depends on civic contributors and it can be difficult to "recruit" them. Such a situation requires a critical reflection about various issues: Are the expected contributions too much to ask? Is the timeframe no realistic (too often, wrong weekdays, too spontaneous)? Have certain potential contributors not been approached yet? Is the likely benefit for contributors not explicit enough or not attractive enough? Are signals of appreciation clear enough? Are possible concerns of potential contributors well understood and addressed (e.g. liability)?

Contributors are only motivated by self-interest: It is not a problem per se if civic contributors are motivated by self-interest. On the contrary: Of course, there needs to be something "in there" for them - otherwise it would be exploitation or heroism. As long as the benefits of co-implemented measures reach beyond those who actively contribute all is fine. It goes without saying that no one should be harmed either, although the perception of harm is obviously subjective. What matters in this context is democratic legitimacy during the co-development phase.

Some measures are not suitable for co-implementation: Even something as seemingly banal as a Zebra Crossing cannot simply be painted by well-meaning citizens. The stripes have to have a certain width, special paint needs to be used etc. There are regulations to adhere to, rules to

- Scribe: Responsible for documenting the process, especially to keep a record of important decisions made and a clear reference of the achievements, plans and roles.
- Evaluation Manager: Find someone (person or organisation) who can run the evaluation of the co-implementation process and its results. Such data is important for internal communication (“should we do this again?”) and for external audiences (esp. in case of external funders).
- Communicator: One such person or group should ensure clear and effective communication both within the circle of co-implementors and to the community at large, including the media.

9. **Implement and monitor.** Implementation and monitoring should be undertaken simultaneously in order to allow for adjustments and corrections at a stage when they will have the biggest impact.

10. **Celebrate:** Although this is mentioned last, it is important to have some fun together throughout the entire process. Do not underestimate the importance of humour, a handshake, eye-to-eye conversations, human touch etc.

11. **Welcome newcomers:** Another task that runs throughout the entire process is to remain open to newcomers at any point. This requires a thorough documentation of previous steps for an effective “onboarding” process of people and organisations who wish to join later on.

9. Inspiration

This chapter contains examples of co-implementation in the urban mobility context as well as in other fields. These examples are intended to provide inspiration and a view of the variety of approaches and circumstances in which co-implementation can thrive, rather than providing prescriptions to be followed. Merely mimicking a good practice example is perilous because of the challenge of ascertaining and aligning perfectly with the social, political, economic, and physical context in which the project took place, however as these examples convey, co-implementation is a versatile approach that is possible in many different contexts.

<p>The Bike Waves app, developed by the Austrian company BikeCitizens, utilises crowd-sourced data from cyclists to predict green light phases for the following cyclists, thus making their ride smoother by avoiding stops.⁶</p>	<p>Citizens on bicycles voluntarily “donate” data about their recent trips</p>	<p>No local authority is currently involved. But it could become a strong co-implementation scheme if cities adopt, promote and fund the application of the Bike Waves app.</p>	<p>External funds used to develop the app through a start-up company.</p>
<p>“Cycling Without Age” is a scheme where volunteers drive older residents around their city in rickshaws. The scheme has been implemented by more than 60 Danish local authorities with a total of 2500 volunteers. It is also branching out to over 20 other countries.⁷</p>	<p>Citizen volunteers donate their time. NGOs coordinate the efforts. Older people contribute through story-telling.</p>	<p>The local authorities provide the rickshaws.</p>	<p>Municipal funds.</p>
<p>The municipality of The Hague offered residents the opportunity to swap their parking permit for some green space, a sun terrace etc. in front of their house. Some took up this offer and a few even converted the parking space themselves.⁸ A similar approach is deployed by a number of “Living Streets” initiatives.⁹</p>	<p>Residents agreed to store their car for 6 months in a parking garage and to accept the removal of a parking space; some even contributed their own time and money to this.</p>	<p>The municipality initiated the scheme, organised the logistics and provided funding.</p>	<p>The city council, together with charities, provided €60,000 of funding.</p>
<p>Civic cleaning days are common in a number of cities, for example in Nuremberg under the local dialect</p>	<p>Youth groups, school classes, all kinds of associations</p>	<p>The local waste removal company provides gloves,</p>	<p>Typically combined funding between waste removal</p>

⁶ See <https://www.bikecitizens.net/de/gruene-welle-fuer-radfahrer/>

⁷ See <http://www.govint.org/good-practice/case-studies/cyclingwithout-age-co-production-made-in-denmark/>

⁸ See https://www.theguardian.com/world/2018/may/17/sun-terraces-and-lawns-dutch-residents-transform-parking-spaces?CMP=share_btn_link

⁹ See <https://www.milton-keynes.gov.uk/environmental-health-and-trading-standards/mk-low-carbon-living/living-streets-community-project>

expression “Kehrd wärd ¹⁰ ”. Citizens clean up parks, river banks and other public spaces.	contribute their time and labour.	high-vis vests, brooms, waste bags etc. and collects the garbage for proper disposal.	company and municipality.
Citizen buses complement public transport services in underserved areas. They are typically driven by volunteers but are open to the public at a fare cost that is comparable to normal public transport. ¹¹	Citizens, often retired people with plenty of time, drive buses on regular routes at regular times - almost like a normal bus	Municipalities / public transport operators provide buses, gasoline, insurance, maintenance and know how.	Municipalities co-fund citizen buses just like normal public transport services. Passengers pay a normal fare.

¹⁰ See https://www.nuernberg.de/internet/soer_nbg/kehrdwaerd.html (German website)

¹¹ See for example <http://www.buergerbus-kettwig.de/> (German website)

10. References and resources

Arnstein, S. R. (1969) A Ladder of Citizen Participation. *Journal of the American Planning Association*, Vol. 35, No. 4, July 1969, pp. 216-224.

Bason, C. (2010). *Leading public sector innovation - Co-creating for a better society*. Bristol: Policy Press.

Bisschops, S. and Beunen, R. (2018) A new role for citizens' initiatives: the difficulties in co-creating institutional change in urban planning. *Journal of Environmental Planning and Management*, Vol 62 / 1, pp. 72-87. Retrieved from <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/09640568.2018.1436532>. Last access: 2019, April 30.

Governance International (2016) *Co-Production Star - A toolkit for public services and communities*. Retrieved from http://www.govint.org/fileadmin/user_upload/publications/Co-production_Star_2015.pdf. Last access: 2019, April 30.

Hoogma, R.; Kemp, R.; Schot, J. and Truffer, B. (2002) *Experimenting for Sustainable Transport - The Approach of Strategic Niche Management*. London: Routledge. Open Access at <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/books/9780203994061>

Lydon, M. and Garcia, A. (2015) *Tactical Urbanism - Short-term action for long-term change*. Washington DC: Island Press.

Macharis, C. and Keseru, I. (2018) Rethinking mobility for a human city. *Transport Reviews*, Vol 38 / 3, pp. 275-278. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1080/01441647.2018.1423612>. Last access: 2019, April 30.

Further Resources:

Peer to Peer Foundation: <https://p2pfoundation.net/>

Spaargaren, G., van Bueren, E. et al. (no date) *Co-Creating Sustainable Cities - Learn how citizen's co-creation is key in making cities worldwide more sustainable (Online Course)*. Available at <https://www.edx.org/course/co-creating-sustainable-cities-delftx-wageningenx-ams-urb-2x>

Tactical Urbanism Website: <http://tacticalurbanismguide.com>

The Better Block Project: <http://buildabetterburb.org/better-blocks-in-the-burbs/>

The Neighbourhood Project: <http://theneighbourhoodproject.org/projects/>

The Street Plans Collaborative (2012) Tactical Urbanism Vol. 1. Retrieved from https://issuu.com/streetplanscollaborative/docs/tactical_urbanism_vol.1. Last Access: 2019, April 30.

The Street Plans Collaborative (2012) Tactical Urbanism Vol. 2. Retrieved from https://issuu.com/streetplanscollaborative/docs/tactical_urbanism_vol_2_final. Last Access: 2019, April 30.

The Street Plans Collaborative (2012) Tactical Urbanism Vol. 4. Retrieved from https://issuu.com/codesignstudio/docs/tacticalurbanismvol4_141020. Last Access: 2019, April 30.

